

Effect of salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl) (3 wk stress) on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root of 4 rice varieties and lines.^aFaisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety or line	Fresh wt (g/plant)		Zn ²⁺ (mg/kg dry wt)		P (%)		Zn ²⁺ :P		
	0	100	0	100	0	100	0	100	
	Shoot								
Basmati 370	19.25 a	3.99 c (21)	32.7 d	43.3 b-d	0.224 e	0.281 b	1.46 × 10 ⁻²	1.54 × 10 ⁻²	
NIAB6	19.91 a	7.81 b (39)	41.0 cd	71.3 a	0.163	0.231 d	2.51 × 10 ⁻²	3.09 × 10 ⁻²	
BG402-4	16.52 a	5.94 bc (36)	37.7 d	50.7 b	0.216	0.267 c	1.75 × 10 ⁻²	1.90 × 10 ⁻²	
IR1561	19.50 a	2.96 d (15)	43.3 b-d	51.3 bc	0.231 d	0.287 a	1.87 × 10 ⁻²	1.79 × 10 ⁻²	
Mean	18.80 A	5.18 B	38.7 B	54.7 A	0.208 B	0.266 A	1.64 × 10 ⁻²	2.68 × 10 ⁻²	
	Root								
Basmati 370	21.12 ab	5.98 d (28)	43.3 b	43.3 b	0.131 d	0.157 b	3.30 × 10 ⁻²	2.76 × 10 ⁻²	
NIAB6	19.69 ab	9.46 c (48)	58.7 a	62.3 a	0.127 d	0.157 b	4.62 × 10 ⁻²	3.97 × 10 ⁻²	
BG402-4	18.82 b	10.13 c (54)	56.0 a	56.7 a	0.131 c	0.152 a	4.27 × 10 ⁻²	3.73 × 10 ⁻²	
IR1561	23.12 a	4.10 d (18)	59.7 a	55.0 a	0.141 c	0.195 a	4.23 × 10 ⁻²	2.82 × 10 ⁻²	
Mean	20.55 A	7.42 B	54.4 A	53.3 A	0.132 B	0.165 A	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.32 × 10 ⁻²	

^aMeans with different letters differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05). The Zn²⁺: P ratio is calculated when the concentration of Zn and P is in percent. Values in the parentheses represent percentages of respective controls.

various plant tissues, ionic balance, osmotic adjustment, etc.) are related to a plant's salt tolerance. Many workers have used these physiological traits to screen rice genotypes for salt tolerance. We determined the effect of external salinity on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root. Seedlings of four rice varieties were transferred at 14 d to foam-plugged holes (1 cm diam) in thermoplastic sheets floating on Yoshida nutrient solution at two salinity levels: 0

and 100 mol NaCl in plastic tubs. Plants were harvested after 3 wk, separated into shoot and root, dried, and Zn and P contents determined.

Zn²⁺ concentration in the shoot increased significantly with external salinity of 100 mol NaCl; in the root, it was not affected by salt stress (see table). Zn concentration in the shoot of salt-tolerant NIAB6 was significantly higher than in the other varieties. Zn concentration in roots of NIAB6 was

significantly higher than that of Basmati 370 (which had the lowest Zn²⁺ concentration in shoot and root).

Salt-sensitive IR1561 had significantly higher P concentration in shoot and root than all other varieties; salt-tolerant NIAB6 had significantly lower shoot P concentration than all other varieties.

Zn:P ratios in shoot and root were highest in NIAB6 and lowest in Basmati 370 with and without salt stress. These ratios were also low in IR1561. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Two modern photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties for Bangladesh

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BRRI recently released modern photoperiod-sensitive varieties BR22 and BR23 for T. aman season in Bangladesh.

BR22 was developed from Nizersail/BR51-46-5; BR23 was derived from DA29/ BR4. Both varieties are suitable for late planting in T. aman. Yield potential and disease reactions are comparable to those of existing modern

Grain yield and plant height of 2 new varieties for Bangladesh.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
		1st planting	2d planting
BR22	115	4.4	3.4
BR23	120	4.6	3.7
BR11 (check)	110	3.8	1.3
Nizersail (local check)	132	3.1	2.6

^aAverage of 3 yr at 4 regional stations. 1st planting: 4-15 Aug with 30-d-old seedlings, 2d planting: 15-22 Sep with 40-d-old seedlings.

varieties, but the new varieties yield more than 1 t higher in late plantings (see table).

BR22 has medium bold grain with intermediate amylose content and

moderate resistance to tungro (RTV), bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, sheath blight (ShB), and blast.

BR23 has long slender grain with intermediate amylose content and moderate resistance to RTV, stem rot, ShB, and submergence tolerance. □

RAU4045-2A — a very short duration cultivar for harsh upland environments

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RAU4045-2A (IET9790), a semidwarf variety derived from Fine Gora/ IET2832, has resistance to brown spot and grain discoloration and